

DOI :

Assessment of knowledge, awareness, attitude and perception about Cervical Cancer screening and vaccination among college-going girls of Delhi University, India

Nancy Chakma ^a, Sonali Mahar^a, Divakar Parihar ^a, and Sumant Swain ^b

^a PGDM, International Institute of Health Management Research, New Delhi, India.

^b Assistant Professor, International Institute of Health Management Research, New Delhi, India.

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: The worldwide burden of cervical cancer is exposing a sharp divide between low and middle-income countries including India. This study aimed to evaluate the level of knowledge, awareness, attitudes, and perceptions regarding cervical cancer screening and vaccination among female university students in Delhi, India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted involving 306 female students aged 17-35 years from Delhi University. Data collection utilized a semi-structured questionnaire, and analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 22. **RESULTS:** The study revealed that 70.6% of participants were familiar with cervical cancer, yet only 20.3% knew screening tests. Awareness of risk factors and the connection between HPV and cervical cancer was found to be limited. Participants primarily obtained information from social media platforms and family members. The main obstacles to screening and vaccination were identified as insufficient information (83.4%), concerns about adverse effects (62.9%), and financial constraints (58%). Notably, only 60.5% of respondents expressed willingness to receive the HPV vaccine. **CONCLUSION:** The results indicate a significant gap in the comprehensive understanding of cervical cancer, screening methods, and HPV vaccination among young female college students. These findings emphasize the crucial need for targeted public awareness initiatives and suggest considering the integration of HPV vaccination into India's national immunization program as a strategy to address cervical cancer.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Vaccination, Screening, Female, Students, Delhi University, Low and middle-income countries.

BACKGROUND

In 2020, the World Health Organisation anticipated that there would be 342,000 deaths and 604 000 new instances of cervical cancer globally, making it the fourth most common disease among women. [2,3,6,7]. The projections from 2018 to 2030 suggest a concerning trend, anticipating a surge in the annual count of new cervical cancer cases from 570,000 to 700,000. Additionally, without intervention, the yearly number

Dr. Sumant Swain, Assistant Professor,

International Institute of Health Management Research,
Sector 18 A, Plot no 3, Dwarka, New Delhi, Pin:110067, India.

E-Mail ID:sumanta.swain@gmail.com

ORCID ID:https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2513-1739

© The Author(s) 2024. Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

For reprints contact: voiceforvoiceless2013@gmail.com

Received	Reviewed	Accepted	Published
02-Feb.-2024	27-Mar.-2024	22-Apr.-2024	10-Jun.-2024

Volume	Issue	June	ISSN
No. 6	No. 1	2024	2583-1852(P), 2584-0878(O)

How to Cite this Article: Chakma, Nancy; Mahar, Sonali; Parihar, Divakar; And Swain, Sumant. Assessment of knowledge, awareness, attitude and perception about Cervical Cancer screening and vaccination among college-going girls of Delhi University, India. THE THIRD VOICE REALITY AND VISION. 2024. Vol No-6. Issue No-1. June. Pp: 56-62. DOI

ACCESS THIS ARTICLE ONLINE

Quick Response Code:

Available online at :

thirdvoice.voiceforvoiceless.in

DOI:

Article No - TVRV00058

of fatalities is expected to escalate from 311,000 to 400,000 during the same period (World Health Organization, 2020). This underscores the urgent need for comprehensive measures to address this significant public health issue.

The worldwide burden of cervical cancer is not equitably distributed, exposing a sharp divide between low and middle-income countries and their high-income peers. The incidence of cervical cancer is around twice as high in low- and middle-income nations, with these regions experiencing death rates three times higher than their high-income counterparts (World Health Organization, 2020). This disparity in health emphasizes how critical it is to allocate resources and implement focused treatments to address the unique problems that various socioeconomic groups confront.

It is essential to investigate the variables behind the elevated incidence and death rates linked to cervical cancer in order to fully appreciate the seriousness of the problem. Several elements play a role in this global health concern, including limited access to preventive measures such as vaccination against human papillomavirus (HPV), inadequate screening programs, and challenges in accessing timely and effective treatment options. Understanding these factors is essential for developing holistic strategies to combat cervical cancer on a global scale. At present, there is a noticeable deficiency in program-based cancer screening efforts, resulting in a significant delay in patients reporting symptoms to the healthcare system. This delay can be attributed to a general lack of awareness about cancer. Recognizing the importance of context-specific approaches, the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes the need for research aimed at identifying barriers and crafting practical solutions. By advocating for such research, the WHO underscores the significance of tailoring interventions to the specific needs and challenges encountered in diverse communities.

This paper attempts to determine the level of consciousness among female students on the symptoms, risk factors, and preventative strategies associated with cervical cancer, assess people's knowledge of the various screening techniques to find any myths or beliefs that might affect how people screen where appropriate, to determine obstacles or explanations for not taking part in routine screening.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The data collection was conducted among various colleges of Delhi University. Descriptive and cross-sectional studies were carried out from 23 August 2023 to 1st March 2024 involving 300 college-going female students between the age group of 17-35 years, who were enrolled in both undergraduate and postgraduate programmes of Delhi University. The University of Delhi is a central university located in Delhi, India (24). We selected Delhi University as it is a major university and students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds nationwide attend its campuses. A convenient sampling technique was carried out using a semi-structured questionnaire made via Google Forms and its link was shared with the students via WhatsApp and mail, the questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions only. Seven questions in the knowledge section assessed general knowledge on cervical cancer and screening; eight questions in the awareness section measured knowledge of cervical cancer screening; eight questions in the practice section measured knowledge of cervical cancer vaccination; and four questions measured perception of cervical cancer. The socio-demographic information on age and religion history served as independent factors. The knowledge, awareness, attitude and practice sections served as dependent variables. There were two inclusion criteria – one was college going girls of the reproductive age group of 17-35 years and the participants were students of Delhi university. The exclusion criteria was – Men, women outside the age limit and the women who underwent hysterectomy. Five students participated in a pilot study to see whether the questions were correct and heading in the right direction, the study was then corrected and modified as necessary. The questionnaire consisted of 30 questions which had 4 sections on socio demographic profile, knowledge on cervical cancer, risk factors, sources of information awareness about cervical cancer screening and vaccination, knowledge on PAP test, the interrelation between HPV and cervical cancer, and their attitude towards cervical cancer screening. The option “I don't know” was added to the knowledge field to prevent an incomplete survey. The questionnaire contained both English and Hindi language. Informed consent was taken before proceeding with the interview. Missing and incomplete unanswered questionnaires were removed and before analyzing the data, the team ensured that the data was correct and comprehensive. IBM SPSS 22 was used for the analysis of data. The study was approved by the Student Institutional Review Board of The International Institute of Health Management Research.

To compile all pertinent data from the field, a thorough literature study was carried out utilising mesh terminology like as cervical cancer, cervical cancer & KAP, North & South India, Validity & Reliability of KAP Questionnaires, Cervical Cancer in India, Prevention of Cervical Cancer and Cervical Cancer Pathology. The subjects were informed about the study's aim, focus, and questionnaire. Data was obtained once the consent was in writing. The consistency and completeness of the questionnaires were examined.

RESULTS

A total of 306 participants were included in this study. Out of which 257 (84%) of the participants were Hindu, 13 (4.2%) were Christians, and 13 (4.2%) were Muslims. Buddhists made up 12 (3.9%) of the participants, while the remaining participants were of other religions (Sikh, Meitei, Jain, Bathouism, Indigenous and Animism). 17 to 19-year-olds made up the bulk of the participants and were enrolled in the undergraduate programmes. The mean age was 18.92. Students doing undergraduate were 301 (98.4%) and Post graduation 5 (1.6%). (table no. 1)

Table No. 1- Socio- demographic information of participating girls in Delhi University

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percent
Age (n=299)	17-19 yrs	213	71.2
	20-22 yrs	85	28.4
	23-25 yrs	1	0.3
Religion (n=306)	Hindu	257	84
	Christian	13	4.2
	Islam	13	4.2
	Others	23	7.5
Education (n=306)	Post Graduation	5	1.6
	Under Graduation	301	98.4

About 216 (70.59%) students had heard about the Cervical Cancer whereas 90(29.41%) had no idea about or some were relating Cervical pain with the Cervical Cancer. (Fig. No. 1)

Fig. 1 - Students who have heard about the Cervical Cancer.

Out of 306 students, 212 (69.3%) students had no idea about the risk factor and 94 (30.7%) students said HPV Infections and Poor genital hygiene were the main risk factors for cervical cancer. Whether HPV & Cervical cancer are interrelated, 243 students said they are not related whereas 63 students said they are related. (Table no. 2) Social media and Family were most among the information sources of the cervical cancer. Healthcare professionals, Teachers, and newspapers were also indicated among the information sources. (Fig. No 2)

Fig. 2 - Information sources about Cervical Cancer.

Only 62 (20.3%) students had heard about the screening test for cervical cancer. On asking who should get tested the major response was any female i.e. 66%. (Table no. 2)

Table No. 2 -Women's knowledge on cervical cancer, screening, and risk factors

Variable	Yes n(%)	No n (%)
Heard about Cervical Cancer (n= 306)	216 (70.6%)	90 (29.4%)
HPV & cervical cancer are interrelated	63 (20.6%)	243 (79.4%)
Risk Factors (n=306)		
HPV Infections	56(59.5%)	
Poor genital hygiene	55(58.5%)	
Uterine Infections	43(45.7%)	
Multiple Sex Partners	36(38.2%)	
Family History	28(29.7%)	
Oral Contraceptive Use	27(28%)	
Heard PAP test (n=306)	62(20.3%)	244(79.7)
Who should get Tested (n= 306)		
Any female	202 (66.0)	
Female Sex workers	7 (2.3)	
Only married women	6 (2.0)	
Unmarried women	10 (3.3)	
I don't know	81(26.5)	
How often one needs to do a PAP test (n=62)		
Every 1 year	14(4.6)	
Every 3 year	9(2.9)	
Every 6 Month	18(5.9)	
Do not know	21(6.9)	

Only 5 out of 306 students have gone for screening for cervical cancer. When they were asked that why they haven't gotten screened majority of the students said they had no knowledge or they have no symptoms regarding cervical cancer. Surprisingly some students also said that they had no time for the screening.

Lack of information (83.4%) , fear of side effects (62.9%) and financial concerns (58%) were major barriers found in getting vaccination or screening for Cervical cancer. (Table no. 3)

Table No. 3 - Practice Towards Screening of Cervical Cancer & HPV Vaccination among college going girls

Variable	Frequency n (%)
Why haven't you gotten screened?	
No Knowledge	196 (64%)
No Symptoms	196 (64%)

Not Advised	158 (51.6%)
Not Needed	87 (28.4%)
No Time	20 (0.06%)
No Money	26 (0.8)
Barriers in getting in HPV Vaccination for Cervical cancer	
Financial Concerns	98 (58%)
Lack of Information	151 (83.4%)
Fear of Side Effects	114 (62.9%)
Cultural or Social Stigma	46 (25.4%)
Accessibility Issues	62 (34.2%)

When asked about willingness to take HPV vaccine 185 (60.5%) students said they are willing, 121(39.5%) students were not willing to take HPV vaccine. (Fig. No. 3 & 4)

Fig. 3 Students Willingness to know regarding the Cervical Cancer

Fig. 4 - Students who are willing to take HPV Vaccine

DISCUSSION

Although uterine cervical cancer is a common illness among Indian women, it is curable with early diagnosis. The main way to avoid cervical cancer is to get vaccinated against HPV, which shields women against oncogenic variants of the virus, which cause most occurrences of cervical cancer (17). The main objective of this study was to collect data on girls at Delhi University's level of knowledge and comprehension regarding HPV, cervical cancer, and attitudes toward HPV vaccination. This data may be useful in developing successful vaccination campaigns and efficient HPV screening programs for the prevention of cervical cancer. It has been noted that girls have lower knowledge about HPV as the primary cause of cervical cancer. Furthermore, none of the girls recognized the PAP smear screening examination. This demonstrates how little they know and comprehend about cervical cancer. Numerous studies were conducted to examine young women's knowledge of HPV and cervical cancer in both rural and urban areas of India [18–19] as well as in other nations [15–17, 21]. These studies all show that young undergraduate and graduate students from both rural and urban areas have very little awareness and understanding about cervical cancer.

Family members, medical professionals, and social media were the most often mentioned information sources. Since most girls indicated a lack of knowledge of cervical cancer [14], followed by the fear of the HPV vaccine's negative effects was cited as one of the primary reasons for not being examined and vaccinated. Providing information can encourage and inspire women to participate in screening and vaccination programs. This study has a few possible limitations. Our survey was limited to female students at Delhi University in the metropolis, and it does not include replies from rural or medical/engineering/law students. Because of the small sample size of a focused demographic, the study's conclusions cannot be generalized to the larger Indian women population or those outside of institutions.

CONCLUSION

According to this study, young women in college have low overall awareness and understanding of HPV, cervical cancer, PAP testing, and the HPV vaccine. The lack of a state-wide cervical screening and awareness campaign has resulted in a lack of knowledge of risk factors for cervical cancer among these young women, regardless of literacy level. The HPV vaccine is our best

prevention against HPV-related cancers. India has a strong track record of childhood immunizations and, more recently, COVID-19 vaccines. Incorporating the HPV vaccine into the national immunization schedule will surely help the fight against cervical cancer. Any such initiative should be followed by an effective public awareness campaign.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

NC, SM, DP and SS conceptualized and designed the study. NC, SM, and DP designed the study tool, collected data, analyzed and interpreted the data, and drafted the manuscript. SS contributed to the thorough review and editing of the final manuscript. All the authors provided critical input on the paper, read and approved the final paper. SS takes responsibility as a guarantor for this research article.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the International Institute of Health Management (IIHMR) student research board.

Informed Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank all the participants who patiently participated in this study. Thanks to the International Institute of Health Management (IIHMR), New Delhi, India for providing support and cooperation to complete this research.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT AND SPONSORSHIP

Nil.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Garg P, Srivastava S, Shumayla S, Kurian K, Rehman A, Garg R, et al. Women's Knowledge on Cervical Cancer Risk Factors and Symptoms: A Cross Sectional Study from Urban India. Asian Pacific

- Journal of Cancer Prevention. 2022 Mar 1;23(3):1083–90.
2. Srivastava S, Kurian K, Garg P, Aziz Ur Rehman, Garg R, Suresh Kumar Rathi, et al. Prevalence and Predictors of Cervical Cancer Screening among Reproductive Age Group Women: Evidence from Cross-Sectional Study in Rohtak and Delhi. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention* [Internet]. 2022 Aug 1;23(8):2771–7.
 3. Muthuramalingam MR, Muraleedharan VR. Patterns in the prevalence and wealth-based inequality of cervical cancer screening in India. *BMC Women's Health*. 2023 Jun 26;23(1).
 4. Dany M, Chidiac A, Nassar AH. Human papillomavirus vaccination: Assessing knowledge, attitudes, and intentions of college female students in Lebanon, a developing country. *Vaccine*. 2015 Feb;33(8):1001–7.
 5. Srinivas V, Herbst de Cortina S, Nishimura H, Krupp K, Jayakrishna P, Ravi K, et al. Community-based Mobile Cervical Cancer Screening Program in Rural India: Successes and Challenges for Implementation. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*. 2021 May 1;22(5):1393–400.
 6. Sharma P, Khanna D, Pradhan S, Praveen Birur. Community cancer screening at primary care level in Northern India: determinants and policy implications for cancer prevention. *Family Medicine and Community Health* [Internet]. 2023 Dec 1 [cited 2024 Jan 19];11(Suppl 1):e002397–7.
 7. Misra M, Tiwari V, Tripathi P. Awareness, Attitude and Practices Regarding Cervical Cancer Screening and Vaccination among North Indian Women Population. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*. 2020;08(03):73–88.
 8. Oct-Dec 2020 - Volume 64 - Issue 4 : *Indian Journal of Public Health* [Internet]. journals.lww.com. [cited 2024 Jan 19].
 9. Singh E, Seth S, Rani V, Srivastava DK. Awareness of cervical cancer screening among nursing staff in a tertiary institution of rural India. *Journal of Gynecologic Oncology*. 2012;23(3):141.
 10. Patra S, Upadhyay M, Chhabra P. Awareness of cervical cancer and willingness to participate in screening program: Public health policy implications. *Journal of Cancer Research and Therapeutics*. 2017;13(2):318.
 11. Jain S, Bagde M, Bagde N. Awareness of cervical cancer and Pap smear among nursing staff at a rural tertiary care hospital in Central India. *Indian Journal of Cancer*. 2016;53(1):63.
 12. Sharma C, Singh P, Arora I, Bhardwaj A, Saini A, Gothwal M, et al. Assessment of understanding about human papilloma virus vaccination among undergraduate medical students in a developing country: Perspective from India. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 2020;9(8):4311.
 13. Manikandan S, Behera S, Naidu N, Angamuthu V, Mohammed OB, Debata A. Knowledge and awareness toward cervical cancer screening and prevention among the professional college female students. *Journal of Pharmacy And Bioallied Sciences* [Internet]. 2019;11(6):314
 14. Rashid S, Labani S, Das BC. Knowledge, Awareness and Attitude on HPV, HPV Vaccine and Cervical Cancer among the College Students in India. Natarajaseenivasan K, editor. *PLOS ONE*. 2016 Nov 18;11(11):e0166713.
 15. Bendik MK, Mayo RM, Parker VG. Knowledge, perceptions, and motivations related to HPV vaccination among college women. *J Cancer Educ*. 2011;26: 459–464. pmid:21336980
 16. Lenselink CH, Schmeink CE, Melchers WJG, Massuger L FAG, Hendriks JCM, van Hamont D, et al. Young adults and acceptance of the human papillomavirus vaccine. *Public Health*. 2008;122: 1295–301. pmid:18619631
 17. Arbyn M, Anttila A, Jordan J, Ronco G, Schenck U, Segnan N, et al. European guidelines for quality assurance in cervical cancer screening. Second edition—Summary document. *Ann Oncol*. 2010;21:448–58.
 18. Awareness of Cervical Cancer Among Female Students of Premier Colleges in Kolkata, India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*, 2010; 11(4): 1085-1090.
 19. Sharma K, Kathait A, Jain A, Kujur K, Raghuwanshi S, Bharti AC, et al. Higher prevalence of human papillomavirus infection in adolescent and young adult girls belonging to different Indian tribes with

- varied socio-Sexual lifestyle. PLoS One. 2015;10: 1–13. pmid:25954813
20. Taneja N, Chawla B, Awasthi AA, Shrivastav KD, Jaggi VK, Janardhanan R. Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice on Cervical Cancer and Screening Among Women in India: A Review. *Cancer Control*. 2021 Jan 1;28:107327482110107.
21. Mongsawaeng C, Kokorn N, Kujapun J, Norkaew J, Kootanavanichpong N, Chavenkun W, et al. Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Regarding Cervical Cancer among Rural Community Women in Northeast Thailand. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*. 2016 Feb 5;17(1):85–8.
- 22 . Sivasubramanian N, Beeman M, Bharatbhai Patel U, Payalben V, R A, Gnanadesigan E. Knowledge on cervical cancer among Indian women in the state of Gujarat. *Bioinformation* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Feb 12];19(10):999–1002.
23. Ruddies, Friederike, et al. “Cervical Cancer Screening in Rural Ethiopia: A Cross- Sectional Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Study.” *BMC Cancer*, vol. 20, 17 June 2020, www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7298871/, https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-020-07060-4.
24. Delhi. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delhi. 2024 [cited 2024 Feb 12].